

Designing Whale Watching Materials and Training Courses for Tourism Guides of Ecuador.

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INTRODUCTION

Whale watching is one of the fastest growing tourism industries in the world. In 1998, this industry was estimated to be worth US\$1 billion worldwide, and it continues to grow at a 12.1% rate per year. It was estimated that in 2008 alone, 886.000 people went whale watching in Latin American countries, resulting in US \$278 million in direct and indirect expenditures (Hoyt & Iñiguez, 2008). Ecuador is amongst the top 5 whale-watching destinations in Latin America (Hoyt & Iñiguez, 2008).

Ecuador is a small country with a coastline that extends over 640km, and that is situated in the southeast Pacific of South America. It has a population of 16,000.000 people occupying 24 different provinces, 6 of which are located on the coastal line of the country and are the home of almost half of the nation's population (INEC, 2013). Ecuador supports a growing whale watching industry that receives the Southern Hemisphere humpback whale population every year. La Isla de La Plata, part of Machalilla National Park and Puerto Lopez, was the first place in Ecuador to offer whale watching tours.

The Ecuadorian Ministry of Tourism, along with the Pacific Whale Foundation, created a program to promote and implement responsible marine tourism practices in Ecuador, to help minimize the impact of whale-watching on cetacean populations. This program trained naturalistic guides and guides specialized in whale watching, who work on whale-watching vessels and are also in direct contact with visitors. The program consisted of workshops, seminars and conferences, and included the creation of the First Whale Watching Manual of Ecuador, as well as visual materials and booklets to be used during whale watching tours and shared with visitors/tourists. The Whale Watching Manual mentioned above is the summary of the 2017 whale watching training workshop that was part of the Responsible and Conscious Tourism Project of Ecuador (*Proyecto de Turismo Responsable y Conciencia del Ecuador*)

METHODS & RESULTS

Training program: implementation, planning and execution

Workshops, planning and execution

The project started in August 2017 and was finalized in March 2018. Based on their whale-watching and tourism activity (i.e. presence of whale-watching operators) several coastal communities along the coast of Ecuador were selected to participate in the project. These communities were: Atacames, Sua, Tonsupa, Portete, Puerto Lopez, Salango, Machalilla, Ayangue, Salinas, Santa Elena and Puerto Bolívar (See Figure No. 1). Members of the Pacific Whale Foundation visited these areas and personally handed invitations to naturalistic guides and tour operators to participate in the program.

A total of 102 naturalistic guides (with representation of each of the 11 coastal communities previously selected) successfully participated and finished the program. These coastal communities are found within these 5 Ecuadorian provinces: Esmeraldas, Manabí, Santa Elena, Guayas and el Oro (See Figure No. 1).

The program consisted of 3 workshops and several seminars, and lasted a total of 3 days, 8 hours daily (See Photo No. 2-10). It was carried out in the provinces of Esmeraldas, Manabi and Santa Elena, all in Ecuador. Seminars and workshops focused on the following topics: Cetacean Biology, Behavior, citizen science, and the long and short term impact of whale watching on cetacean populations, specifically on humpback whales. All guides that successfully completed the course/workshop were given an accreditation document to confirm attendance and completion of the program.

Design and distribution of Whale Watching Manual and Visual Material

Marine Biologists and other researches of the Pacific Whale Foundation worked with a professional graphic designer to create a Whale Watching Manual. This Manual focuses on the following topics: Biology, Ecology, Citizen Science, and impact of whale watching tourism on humpback whale and other marine populations.

One thousand copies of this manual (See Photo No. 1) were printed and given out to naturalistic guides, tour operators, local authorities and local media. An additional one thousand copies of booklets/visual aids with a summary of the manual were printed and laminated to be used during whale-watching tours so that visitors can read it. These materials are printed in Spanish (local language) and English. The Whale Watching Manual can be accessed through the following link (Library of the Ecuadorian Tourism Ministry)

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L3eb8HFS5zPXJK2p8zFgpYP7nNutFbOE/view>

Attachments

Figure 1. Coastal map of Ecuador showing all the provinces that offer whale watching tourism. Castro & Cardenas, 2017

Photo #1. Whale Watching Manuals and Booklets handed out to guides during the workshop.

Photo #2. Naturalistic guides from Puerto Lopez at one of the seminars.

Photo # 3. Paola Martinez, naturalistic guide of Machalilla National Park, interpreting humpback whale behavior.

Photo # 4. Julio Pin, Naturalistic Guide of Machalilla National Park, displaying the visual material given at the end of the program and educating visitors about humpback whales and responsible tourism.

Photos #5 #6. Biologist Cristina Castro, PhD, talking about cetacean adaptations to marine life. Salinas, Ecuador. Naturalistic Guides observing and manipulation baleens from a humpback whale

Photo # 7. A representative of the Ministry of Tourism and Cristina Castro, PhD, training naturalistic guides on how to properly use the visual material and engage with visitors before whale watching tours.

Photo # 8. Naturalistic Guides during a workshop. Atacames, Esmeraldas.

Photo # 9. Scarlenth, Olga, Gisella and Zandra, all naturalistic guides learning about humpback whale anatomy (both in English and Spanish) - Esmeralda.

Photo # 10. Whale Watching vessel leaving to go on a tour.

LITERATURE CITED

- Hoyt, E. and Iñíguez, M. 2008. The State of Whale Watching in Latin America. WDCS, Chippenham, UK; IFAW, Yarmouth Port, USA; and Global Ocean, London, 60pp
- INEC Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas y Censos. 2013. <http://www.ecuadorencifras.gob.ec/>